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大连理工大学
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Preparation and Characterization of a Ternary Eutectic $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ Ceramic Composite

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Outline of presentation

- 1. Introduction and background**
- 2. Objectives**
- 3. Materials and Experimental Procedures**
- 4. Results and discussion**
- 5. Summary**

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1. Introduction and background

◆ Characteristics of Al_2O_3 Based Eutectic Composite

TEM morphology of Al_2O_3 /YAG eutectic

- Fine homogeneous in-situ microstructure containing a huge amount of **clean low-energy interfaces** between two strongly bonded phases.
- Excellent mechanical properties, thermal stability, and oxidation resistance in atmosphere at high temperature (up to 1600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$).

1. Introduction and background

◆ Application of Al_2O_3 Based Eutectic Composite

- Ultra-high-temperature materials for aerospace, jet aircraft engine, and gas turbine system applications.

Research targets components for gas turbine:
(a) combustor liners; (b) hollow turbine nozzle

1. Introduction and background

The flexural strength of ceramics :

$$\sigma = \left[\frac{K_{IC}}{0.65 \cdot \sqrt{\pi}} \right] \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{a_c}}, \quad a_c : \text{critical defect size}$$

$$\sigma \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda}}$$

$$\lambda \approx a_c$$

Relationship between critical defect size a_c and interphase spacing λ

Strength σ vs. interphase spacing λ

ICCM22 Higher strength of eutectic ceramics could be achieved by refining microstructure which accompanies with the reducing of flaw sizes.

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Microstructure refinement approaches of melt-grown Al_2O_3 based eutectic bulks.

The microstructure size relates to

- (1) **ambient conditions** (such as **cooling rate**, temperature gradient, heterogeneous nucleation sites, et al.) ^[1].
- (2) **the melt inherent properties** (such as melt viscosity, **composition**);

---[1] G.Q. Chen et al./ *Ceramics International* 39 (2013) 7445–7452

Effect of growth rate on the flexural strength of ceramics

$$\sigma = \left[\frac{K_{IC}}{0.65 \cdot \sqrt{\pi}} \right] \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{a_c}}, \quad a_c : \text{critical defect size}$$

Strength σ vs. interphase spacing λ

$$\sigma \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda}}$$

$$\lambda \approx a_c$$

Critical defect size a_c and interphase spacing λ vs. growth rate ν

The growth rate increases, the microstructure refines accompanying with the reducing of flaw sizes, and the strength increases, accordingly.

Microstructure refinement approaches of melt-grown Al_2O_3 based eutectics.

Further improvements in the mechanical properties can be achieved by manipulating the microstructure **through changes in the solidification rate.**

Thus, several processing techniques for the eutectic oxide ceramic mainly include **laser heated floating zone, edge-defined film-fed growth, micro-pulling down** and **Bridgman method.**

◆ Previous Researches on the Al₂O₃ Based Eutectic Composite

■ Processing techniques:

- Laser heated floating zone (LHFZ);
- Edge-defined film-fed growth (EFG);
- Micro-pulling down (μ-PD);

Thermal gradient

$$G > 10^4 \text{ K/cm}$$

— Faster growth rates attained lead to fine microstructure and high strength.

- Bridgman method.

$$G \leq 10^2 \text{ K/cm}$$

— Optimum to prepare the large volume samples.

■ Processing techniques:

LHFZ

EFG

μ-PD

Bridgman

The dimensions of products are limited to **several millimeters**.

Prepare the large volume samples

◆ Limiting factor for the wider engineering application.

- Difficult to prepare the samples with both **large dimensions** and **homogeneous fine microstructures**. The reasons are as follows:
 - (1) **Large-size samples** require to have a lower temperature gradient.
——Higher thermal gradient may lead to the occurrence of cracking in large volume samples.
 - (2) **Homogeneous fine microstructures** demand higher thermal gradient and growth rate v .

Jackson-Hunt law: $\lambda^2 v = K$ [1], λ is the interphase spacing.

[1] Jackson K A, Hunt J D. AIME Met Soc Trans, 1966,236:1129-1142.

1. Introduction and background

How to obtain the fine microstructure in the large-size ceramic samples ?

The microstructure size relates to

(1) **ambient conditions** (such as **cooling rate**, temperature gradient, heterogeneous nucleation sites, et al.) ^[1].

(2) **the melt inherent properties** (such as melt viscosity, **composition**);

---[1] G.Q. Chen et al./ *Ceramics International* 39 (2013) 7445–7452

Microstructure refinement approaches of melt-grown Al_2O_3 based eutectics.

Further refinements of the eutectic microstructure **can be achieved by the addition of more components** to increase the melt viscosity and decrease the growth length scales.

---Oliete P. B. *Advanced Materials*, 2007, 19(17): 2313-2318.

Microstructure refinement approaches of melt-grown Al_2O_3 based eutectics.

Example:

$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}$ eutectic

$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}/\text{ZrO}_2$ eutectic

Under the same solidification conditions, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}/\text{ZrO}_2$ ternary eutectic has a finer structure than the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{YAG}$ binary eutectic.

2. Research objectives

How to optimize the microstructure in the large-size Y_2O_3 doped $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2$ eutectic ceramic samples?

❖ Research works in our team

Research objects:

Effect of Y_2O_3 addition on the Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 eutectic solidification behaviors was investigated.

Phase diagram of Al_2O_3 - ZrO_2 - Y_2O_3 ternary system[1]

❖ Research works in our team

Composition of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2(\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3)$ eutectics used in the present experiment

Sample (C_0)	Al_2O_3 (mol%)	ZrO_2 (mol%)	Y_2O_3 (mol%)
0.0 mol%	63.0	37.0	0
0.5 mol%	63.0	36.4	0.5
1.1 mol%	63.0	35.9	1.1
1.7 mol%	63.0	35.3	1.7
3.0 mol%	63.0	34.0	3.0
4.5 mol%	63.0	32.5	4.5
5.6 mol%	63.0	31.4	5.6
6.2 mol%	63.0	30.8	6.2
7.0 mol%	63.0	30.0	7.0
8.3 mol%	63.0	28.7	8.3
9.2 mol%	63.0	27.8	9.2

3. Experimental Procedures

❖ Technical route:

- The acquisition of **large-size samples** was prepared by the conventional casting method

Powder synthesis

Melting temperature: 1950 °C
Temperature gradient: $<10^2$ K/cm
Cooling rate: 10 °C/min

Sintering

Melting and solidifying

4. Results and discussion

For the Y_2O_3 doped Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 system, the effect of Y_2O_3 concentration on the **microstructure characteristic, interphase spacing and the formation of $Al_2O_3/ZrO_2/YAG$ ternary eutectic** was investigated, respectively.

❖4.1 Effect of Y_2O_3 concentration on the microstructure

Microstructure of melt-grown Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 eutectic rods as a function of Y_2O_3 content (mol%)

When Y_2O_3 content increases,

- ◆ **Morphology: cellular \rightarrow dendrite;**
- ◆ **The colony size decreases and intercolony area increases;**
- ◆ **Gray phases appear at higher Y_2O_3 content (>4.5 mol%);**

➤ Calculation of constitutional supercooling criterion

For the steady-state growth of an interface, **the equilibrium temperature for any point in front of the interface** was given

$$T_l = T_m - mC_l = T_m - mC_0 \left[1 + \left(\frac{1-k}{k} \right) \exp \left(-\frac{vx}{D} \right) \right] \quad (1)$$

The temperature gradient in front of the interface may be expressed as

$$T = \left(T_m - m \frac{C_0}{k} \right) + Gx \quad (2)$$

The discrimination of constitutional supercooling has been theoretically proposed as follows:

$$\left(\frac{dT}{dx} \right)_{x=0} < \left(\frac{dT_l}{dx} \right)_{x=0} \quad (3)$$

The inequation (3) can be further written as

$$\frac{G}{v} < \frac{mC_0}{D} \frac{1-k}{k} \quad (4)$$

➤ Calculation of constitutional supercooling criterion

Physical parameters used for the calculation.

Parameters	Values	Reference
D (cm ² /s)	1×10^{-6}	approx.
\bar{k}	0.58	calc.
\bar{m} (C/mol%)	9.75	calc.

Equilibrium liquidus temperature calculated at different Y_2O_3 content, as functions of distance ahead of the interface.

Constitutional supercooling criterion [2]:

----When Y_2O_3 content increases, the supercooled zone length δ become much larger.

-----[1] G.Q. Chen et al. / Scripta Materialia 129 (2017) 20–24

-----[2] Tiller W A et al. Acta Metallurgica, 1953,1(4):428-437

❖ Effect of Y_2O_3 concentration on the growth interface

Evolution model of the interface shape as a function of the Y_2O_3 content

For Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 eutectic ceramic, when Y_2O_3 content increases, the growth interface changes obviously from cellular into the dendritic shape.

— This is similar to the solidification behavior of the impure metals and metallic alloys.

❖ Effect of Y_2O_3 concentration on the structure

(a) XRD patterns of Y_2O_3 doped Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 eutectics, (b) 4.5 mol% sample

Crystal structures of Y_2O_3 doped Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 melt-grown eutectic ceramic bulks

Samples (C_0 /mol%)	0	0.5	1.1	1.7	3.0	≥ 4.5
Crystal Structures	$\alpha+m$	$\alpha+m+t$	$\alpha+m+t$	$\alpha+t+c$	$\alpha+c$	$\alpha+c+Y$

Note: α : $\alpha-Al_2O_3$; m: m- ZrO_2 ; t: t- ZrO_2 ; c: c- ZrO_2 ; Y: YAG.

When Y_2O_3 content increases,

◆ The crystal structures of ZrO_2 phase:

monoclinic (m- ZrO_2) \rightarrow tetragonal (t- ZrO_2) \rightarrow cubic (c- ZrO_2)

YAG phase may appear at higher Y_2O_3 content (>4.5 mol%).

❖ Effect of Y_2O_3 concentration on the structure

EDS analysis on 4.5 mol% sample

EPMA analysis on 4.5 mol% sample

- The Y_2O_3 content in the inter-colony region is higher than that inside the colony.
 — Y_2O_3 segregation occurred during the solidification.
- For higher Y_2O_3 content samples (≥ 4.5 mol%), the **YAG phase (gray phase) or Al_2O_3 - ZrO_2 - $Y_3Al_5O_{12}$ ternary eutectic** formed in the intercolony region.

❖ 4.2 Formation mechanism of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2/\text{YAG}$ ternary eutectic in the intercolony region

❖ 4.2 Volume fraction of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2/\text{YAG}$ ternary eutectic in the intercolony region

The volume fraction of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2/\text{YAG}$ ternary eutectic will increase with the increase of Y_2O_3 content.

❖ 4.2 Volume fraction of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2/\text{YAG}$ ternary eutectic in the intercolony region

Quantitative determination of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2/\text{YAG}$ ternary eutectic can be accomplished **by the point count method.**

❖ 4.2 Volume fraction of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2/\text{YAG}$ ternary eutectic in the intercolony region

Results of metallographic analysis for volume fraction of ternary eutectic

Sample (C_0)	Average number of red area in pixels	Total number of photograph in pixels	Volume fraction of ternary eutectic (vol.%)
0.5 mol%	0	296100	0
1.1 mol%	0	296100	0
1.7 mol%	0	296100	0
3.0 mol%	4413	296100	1.5
4.5 mol%	19858	296100	6.7
5.6 mol%	34359	296100	11.6
6.2 mol%	38789	296100	13.1
7.0 mol%	59570	296100	14.2
8.3 mol%	59516	296100	20.1
9.2 mol%	81327	296100	27.5

❖ 4.2 Volume fraction calculation of Al₂O₃/ZrO₂/YAG ternary eutectic in the intercolony region

▪ Case I: Equilibrium level rule

$$f_E = C_0 / C_E \quad (1)$$

▪ Case II: Nonequilibrium lever rule or Scheil equation

Y₂O₃ content C_s in the solid

$$C_s = kC_0(1 - f_s)^{k-1} \quad (2)$$

According to the definition of the distribution coefficient $k=C_s/C_l$, the mean liquid composition C_l in the inter-dendritic regions

$$C_l = C_0(1 - f_s)^{k-1} \quad (3)$$

When C_l reaches the eutectic composition C_E ($C_l=C_E$), **the volume fraction f_E of the ternary eutectic predicted by the Scheil equation can be expressed as**

$$f_E = 1 - f_s = (C_0 / C_E)^{1/1-k} \quad (4)$$

❖ 4.2 Volume fraction of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2/\text{YAG}$ ternary eutectic in the intercolony region

➤ The volume fraction of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2/\text{YAG}$ ternary eutectic can be well predicted by the Scheil equation (or nonequilibrium lever rule).

❖ 4.3 Effect of Y_2O_3 concentration on the interphase spacing

➤ **There exist some differences in the interphase spacing** inside the colonies between the Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 melt-grown eutectic ceramic samples with different Y_2O_3 contents.

❖ 4.3 Effect of Y_2O_3 concentration on the interphase spacing

Average interphase spacing of the ZrO_2 platelets in the Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 eutectics as a function of Y_2O_3 content estimated by the **mean-intercept method**.

Sample (C_0 /mol%)	0	0.5	1.1	1.7	3.0	4.5
Interphase spacing ($\lambda/\mu m$)	1.82	1.22	1.10	1.32	1.64	1.62
Standard error	0.06	0.05	0.03	0.05	0.06	0.08

$\lambda=1\sim 2 \mu m$

When Y_2O_3 content increases, the interphase spacing λ tends to decrease to a minimum ($\approx 1.1 \mu m$), and then increases slightly.

❖ 4.3 Effect of Y_2O_3 concentration on the interphase spacing

Interphase spacing λ and growth rate v VS. Y_2O_3 content. The growth rate v was calculated according to the $\lambda v^{0.5} = 1 \mu m^{1.5} s^{-0.5}$ [1].

➤ Interphase spacing depends on whether the heat or solute diffusion predominates the crystal growth during the solidification, which is dependent on the solute content——LGK model [2].

5. Summary

- As the Y_2O_3 content increases, the colony morphology of Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 eutectic changes obviously from cellular into the dendritic shape, which is consistent with the classical constitutional supercooling criterion.
- The volume fraction of $Al_2O_3/ZrO_2/YAG$ ternary eutectic in the intercolony region will increase with the increase of Y_2O_3 content. The Scheil equation (or nonequilibrium lever rule) can be applied to predict the amount of ternary eutectic well.
- When the Y_2O_3 content increases, the interphase spacing λ tends to decrease to a minimum ($\approx 1.1 \mu m$), and then increases slightly.

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